

Ionization Constants of some 1-Substituted-3-(2-Pyridyl)-2-Thioureas in Acetonitrile-Water Media

C. S. G. PRASAD and SAMIR K. BANERJI

Chemical Laboratories, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, Rajasthan, 333031, India.

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The ionization constants of various 1-substituted-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thioureas viz., 1-phenyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (PPTH), 1-o-tolyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (OTPTH), 1-p-tolyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (PTPTH), 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (BPTH), and 1-methyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (MPPTH) have been determined pH-metrically in 50% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixtures. The results have been interpreted on the basis of substituent effects. Thermodynamic ionization constants have also been evaluated by extrapolating a plot of ionization constant versus ionic strength to zero ionic strength. Thermodynamic parameters associated with the ionization processes have also been determined.

THE tautomerism of substituted thioureas has not been an active field of study in spite of the undoubted importance of these compounds. Recently in these laboratories the thione-thiol tautomerism of a group of 1-substituted-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thioureas have been studied in detail by the spectro-photometric methods.² It was thought desirable to determine the pK values of these compounds in order to correlate the substituent effects operative in these compounds. The compounds selected for this purpose were 1-phenyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (PPTH), 1-o-tolyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (OTPTH), 1-p-tolyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (PTPTH), 1-benzyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (BPTH), and 1-methyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-2-thiourea (MPPTH).

Experimental

Chemicals: All chemicals used were at least of analytical reagent grade. Acetonitrile (Reidel) was dried over fused calcium chloride and distilled. Carbonate free potassium hydroxide was prepared by the method of Albert and Sarjeant².

Instruments: pH measurements were made on a Beckmann pH-meter (Model H2) using a glass-calomel electrode assembly. The glass electrode had negligible alkali error between 11 and 12 pH. Readings above 12 pH were neglected in the calculations. For maintaining the temperature a thermostatic bath (Forma Scientific, USA, Model 2095) was used.

Technique: The technique used was the direct pH titration technique described by Albert and Sarjeant². 0.01 M solutions of PPTH, OTPTH, PTPTH, BPTH and MPPTH in acetonitrile were equilibrated for 60 hr and the titration was carried out as outlined below. In all the cases the medium was maintained at 50% (v/v)

acetonitrile-water. All pH-meter readings were corrected to this medium by the method of Van Uitert and Hass³.

To 40 ml of 0.01 M solution of the compound (PPTH, OTPTH, PTPTH, BPTH, or MPPTH) were added 10 ml of acetonitrile, sufficient amount of 1 M sodium perchlorate (Reidel) to maintain desired ionic strength, and enough water to make the total volume 100 ml in all cases. To this mixture ten equal aliquots (0.4 ml each) of 0.1 N KOH were added and the pH noted after each addition. The pK values were then calculated using standard equations³. From these values the true pK values at each ionic strength and temperature were evaluated by a least-squares fit.

To determine the thermodynamic pK , pK_T , pK values were determined at 20° at the ionic strengths 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20. A graph of pK vs. ionic strength was then plotted and extrapolated to zero ionic strength whence the pK_T values were obtained. The experiments were repeated at different temperatures (10°, 20°, 30°, and 40°C) at a fixed ionic strength (0.10) to determine the thermodynamic parameters. ΔG was calculated from the equation $\Delta G = RT pK$. ΔH was evaluated from the van't Hoff isotherm and ΔS from the equation $\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G)/T$.

Results

The pK values of all these compounds at various ionic strengths and their thermodynamic ionization constants are presented in Table-1. pK values at different temperatures and the thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH , and ΔS are given in Table-2.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE PK VALUES OF SOME SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS.

Compound	Ionic strength	pK
PPTH	0.05	11.46
	0.10	11.32
	0.15	11.07
	0.20	10.93
	0.00*	11.64
	0.05	11.79
OTPTH	0.10	11.62
	0.15	11.57
	0.20	11.29
	0.00*	11.95
	0.05	11.55
	0.10	11.45
PTPTH	0.15	11.22
	0.20	11.06
	0.00*	11.71
	0.05	11.86
	0.10	11.66
	0.15	11.53
BPTH	0.20	11.36
	0.00*	12.02
	0.05	11.94
	0.10	11.75
	0.15	11.56
	0.20	11.39
MPTH	0.00*	12.12

*By extrapolation.

Note: The studies were carried out at 20 ± 0.1°C.

Discussion

The substituted thioureas taken up for study exhibit a tautomeric equilibrium which may be represented as:

The enethiol form II ionizes as below:

An examination of the thermodynamic pK values shows that these are weak acids (pK 11 to 12). Among these compounds PPTH (pK_T = 11.64, R = -phenyl) is the strongest acid and MPTH (pK_T = 12.12, R = -methyl) is the weakest. The other compounds have intermediate pK values. This can be rationalised on the basis of the electron donor-acceptor properties of the substituent R. The phenyl group can act both as a donor and an acceptor. Assuming it to be an acceptor in the cases of the compounds studied, we see it facilitates the release of the proton by withdrawing electrons from the system -S-C=N. The other substituents all act, basically, as electron donors. Thus the release of proton is more difficult in these cases and hence the higher pK values. The pK_T values of these compounds (OTPTH 11.95, PTPTH 11.71, BPTH 12.02 and MPTH 12.12) correlate well with the electron donor properties of the substituent groups viz., o-tolyl, p-tolyl, benzyl, and methyl. The higher value of pK_T for OTPTH as compared to PTPTH is probably a manifestation of the unusual steric effects associated with the o-tolyl group.

Increasing the temperature leads to a decrease in pK values as is usually observed for most acids at temperatures around room temperatures. The ΔG values are positive indicating that ionization is not spontaneous. The positive values of ΔH show that the reaction is endothermic, while the negative values of ΔS indicate that there is more order in the ionized form than the unionized form.

In a series of papers⁴⁻⁶ Harned and coworkers reported the results of their investigations on the ionization constants (log K) of a variety of acids over a wide range of temperatures. They observed that log K increased with increasing temperature, reached a maximum, and then started decreasing with increasing temperature. Expressing ionization constants in terms of pK rather than log K, we see that pK will decrease with increasing temperature, pass through a minimum, and finally increase with increasing temperature. This minimum pK, termed pK_m, occurs at a definite temperature θ°, which is different for different acids. The difference between pK at any temperature t° and pK_m is a parabolic function of (t - θ).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE IONIZATION AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-3-(2-PYRIDYL)-2-THIOUREAS. IONIC STRENGTH = 0.10

Compound	Temperature (oK)	pK	ΔG (kcal/mole)	ΔH (kcal/mole)	ΔS (cal/mole/deg)
PPTH	283.16	11.46	14.86		
	293.16	11.32	15.19	5.314	-33.68
	303.16	11.19	15.52	(average)	(average)
	313.16	11.07	15.86		
OTPTH	283.16	11.75	15.24		
	293.16	11.62	15.60	3.647	-40.87
	303.16	11.57	16.05	(average)	(average)
	313.16	11.20	16.44		
PTPTH	283.15	11.58	15.01		
	293.16	11.45	15.37	5.153	-34.82
	303.16	11.33	15.72	(average)	(average)
	313.16	11.20	16.05		
BPTH	283.16	11.81	15.31		
	293.16	11.66	15.65	6.752	-30.28
	303.16	11.48	15.93	(average)	(average)
	313.16	11.32	16.23		
MPTH	283.16	11.88	15.40		
	293.16	11.75	15.77	5.322	-35.61
	303.16	11.62	16.13	(average)	(average)
	313.16	11.49	16.47		

TABLE 3—P_{Km}, θ, AND ΔH CALCULATED FROM HARNED'S EQUATION FOR SOME 1-SUBSTITUTED-3-(2-PYRIDYL)-2-THIOUREAS.

Compound	θ°C	pK _m	ΔH(average) (kcal/mole)
PPTH	156.3	10.39	5.318
OTPTH	119.9	11.14	3.834
PTPTH	153.8	10.54	5.215
BPTH	181.8	10.34	6.356
MPTH	160.0	10.75	5.468

$$pK - pK_m = C(t - \theta)^2$$

Where C is a general constant of the order of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ deg}^{-2}$. Expanding and rearranging the above equation we get

$$pK - Ct^2 = pK_m + C\theta^2 - 2C\theta t$$

Thus a plot of $pK - Ct^2$ vs. t should give a straight line of slope $-2C\theta$ and intercept (at $t=0$) $pK_m + C\theta^2$. Such plots were made for all the compounds studied, and the values of pK_m and θ were obtained. These are presented in Table-3.

Harned and co-workers further observed that the true ΔH values for any system could be obtained from the following equation :

$$\Delta H = -2.303 \times 10^{-4} RT^2 (t - \theta)$$

which are of a more fundamental nature than those obtained from equations with arbitrary constants like :

$$\Delta H = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 + \dots + a_nT^n$$

The ΔH values were calculated for all compounds at various temperatures by Harned's equation (Table-3.) and it was observed that these values agreed well with those obtained by temperature coefficient method, thus emphasizing the validity of Harned's assumption that $pK - pK_m$ is a parabolic function of temperature, atleast to a first approximation.

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